

To Study the Consumer Preferences of Instagram On Cafeterias in Sainikpuri, Telangana State

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Abstract:- The present marketing world is shifting from seller based to customer preference based. As now the king of marketing is the customer and the major force acting. This paper derives from a depth study of individual customer choices and opinions on cafes and of using Instagram as a medium to promote cafes. Social Media mostly considered for communication and connecting people across took a major turn by promoting businesses and became a medium to attract people across. Instagram is one such platform that is helping people, irrespective of small- or large-scale business. Cafeterias mostly meant for get together and chilling and consumers preferences changes accordingly. The researchers primarily focused on why and how the consumers preferences affected by Instagram. Studying the consumer preferences is a vast subject to learn as whole. This research paper concentrates about the consumer preferences of Instagram on cafeterias limited to Sainikpuri area. This research paper can be divided into six parts. Firstly, it explains the history of Instagram and cafeterias. The second part will include the discussion of methodology and questionnaire taken to gather the data. This part also includes of literature review implemented and the research gap. The third part consists of the scope of study of this research. In fourth part, the researchers have represented the data collection, descriptive analysis and findings in forms of charts and creative use of graphs and tables. Fifth part consists of the factors affecting business. Finally, the last part includes the conclusion, findings and suggestions of the research.

I. INTRODUCTION

The world runs on internet nowadays. Regardless of the information that one wants to gain, the internet provides you everything. That updated version of searching in internet is social media. According to the top searches of google, social media means as “interactive digital channels that facilitate the creation and sharing of information, ideas, interests, and other forms of expression through virtual communities and networks.” (Article by Burge on social media day, June 30, 2022)

Social media is the collective term for websites and applications that are used for communication, content sharing, marketing etc. In other simple words it is a path for starting, improving, forwarding, learning, and gaining. Any person with entrepreneurial skills would see social media as the best marketing strategy to circulate information about their own products and may even gain innovative ideas through it. Starting from the era of Facebook, the use of social media increased rapidly. According to the studies of yahoo news, by the end of the year 2004 (when Facebook

was launched) there were over 1 million users recorded. This shows how much popularity that social media gained within a year.

Nowadays irrespective of the gender, age, country barriers everyone are connected through social media. It got constantly upgraded over the two decades. One of the most famous updated forms of social media in the present times is INSTAGRAM. Instagram had gained over one billion users in the present year 2022. It provides many features within it with a time-to-time updated versions. Instagram helps to create business accounts. One can create an account and can advertise about their products.

Many small-scale business products are promoted through this Instagram. One such ideas of small-scale business that is popular among all the age groups are cafeterias.

Cafeteria is a place where the consumers are provided with an excellent and comfortable ambience along with the food and drinks with a provided cost. Social media being the game changer of the world, especially changed the world of business. Places like cafeterias usually get famous either through word of mouth or through the social media of food bloggers. Thus, social media has been an effective platform for the cafes to learn more about customer needs and preferences.

Hence, Instagram being the trend promoter of the world also encourages several types of bloggers to share their content and opinions with the public. Various opinions, tastes, ratings, suggestions etc are provided with the help of Instagram to various users. According to the research made by “taking the kitchen”, over 16588 blogs related to food were released on March 31st, 2012(reference from taking the kitchen blog on how many food blogs are there anyway?). Just by rewinding the drastic change of social media that has taken place over the decade will make us assume how much the count have been increased by date.

II. CAFETERIAS IN SAINIKPURI- THE AREA OF BLISS!

Sainikpuri is a small area located in Secunderabad. This area is popularly known for the number of cafes located. Sainikpuri is that part of Secunderabad that attracts many people of different age groups. It is at north-east of Secunderabad which has more than 15 cafes to visit. The ambience, theme or the services provided in all these cafeterias are very well known in the whole twin cities. Nature- the symbol of peace is the common thing that is never avoided in almost all the cafeterias. Keeping the customers comfort as their top priority, they render their best excellent services possible.

III. HISTORY

A. Cafeterias-known since ages!

Every one of us might have spent time in a cafeteria on one day or the other. We might have a great, moderate or a worst experience to share. But have we ever thought where did the idea pop out from? The idea of bringing all the resources like nature, snacks, drinks and peace to a place is an extraordinary idea that had to be appreciated. Earlier people who worked in factories used to have an area for having the meals they brought from their homes which was known as lunchroom back then. It was in 1905, a lady named Helen Mosher had started a small restaurant in the downtown of L.A. in which people had an option of self-service for the first time (reference from Wikipedia on cafeteria in history session). In 1893, a Chicago restaurant owner John Kruger named his place “cafeteria” which was a Spanish word meaning coffee shop. Sometimes if we look back to days, we can feel how far the development of a small idea have been made.

B. Social media- a string that connects the world

Social media was a break fresh for every one of us in the beginning. The first invented social media site was “SIX DEGREES” (reference from CBS news, published on 6th July,2011). It was created in 1997 and however was sold out in 2001. But the social media originally conquered the world by the introduction of Facebook in 2004.

Facebook initially known as face mash was a social media platform created by a thirteen-year-old boy named Mark Zuckerberg. It was just an unofficial site launched by him while he was studying in Harvard university. This was circulated among the youth and later got developed the idea and introduced it in a worldwide sense. People started marketing using this platform called online marketing by posting their products online. Facebook gained over 100 million users within two years and by end of the first decade it gained over 1590 million followers which is more than the triple of its beginning.

However, Facebook was not the only platform that led the social media to heights, but it was just a start of the maniac. In 2005, YouTube was launched, and it had gained its own range of popularity. Later, in 2006 both twitter and FB went worldwide. Other platforms like Tumblr, Spotify, LinkedIn etc took the initiative in its own respective areas.

C. Instagram – the evolution of new era

As said before, even though other social media platforms were a beginning of a new digitalized world, Instagram took the world with it.

Instagram was started in 2010 by Kevin Systrom and Mike Krieger (reference from Wikipedia Instagram). This social media app allows its users to post different pictures, videos, chat with friends and peers, put up a 24-hour story and many more. In the era where the world completely errands on digital inventions, Instagram played a super hyper role in it. The information in Instagram can be given in various new forms like memes, trolls, by a direct video etc. Instagram, along with all these facilities it helps to keep the user content private if they want to and has some

sensitive policies for sensitive contents. It automatically blocks the content which doesn't have copyrights with it. Having such a great kind of features helped itself to gain one million users within two months from the date it launched.

Instagram got updated over the decade. Few updates of Instagram were introducing black and white theme for the app, liking the comments, new image filters, archiving posts, IGTV [long videos more than 1minute] etc. However, they removed this option of IGTV later. The Co-watching feature was introduced recently with the view of COVID-19 pandemic situation. It helped far people to watch memes and videos together through a video call. One such large update in Instagram after banning the Tik-Tok app in few countries is the introduction of “reels” in Instagram. A reel is almost like Tik Tok videos where the users can make a short video of any content they want to share with their followers. This update had taken a drastic change in the usage of Instagram, over 4.34% of Instagram users increased. In 2021, Instagram became the most downloaded app in the entire world beating the Tik-Tok app. (reference from influencer marketing hub article).

D. Objectives:

- To study the overview of Instagram and consumer preference.
- To analyse the factors effecting consumer preferences for cafeteria through Instagram.

IV. LITERATURE REVIEWS

- Evaluation Of Impact of Instagram on Customer Preferences: The Significance of Online market **Year:** February 2020 **Authors:** Dr. Manish Kumar Varma, Nikhil Dhakane, Dr. Avinash Pawar

This paper mainly concentrates on various factors such as gender, age, income, consumer preferences, etc. Sellers should concentrate on these factors and should target their ideal audience. The way online marketing is increasing Instagram will be developed into a powerful and efficient marketing tool for several varieties of businesses.

- The Effects of Instagram Marketing Activities on Customer-Based Brand Equity in the Coffee Industry, 2022 **Authors:** Cho-I Park and Young Namkung

This research paper concentrates on the influences of Instagram marketing activities on customer-based brand equity. The Instagram brand activities affected the brand awareness, brand image, and perceived quality.

- Impact of social media on consumer behaviour, June 2020 **Authors:** Chahat Chopra and Sachin Gupta, Small scale and medium based businesses take full advantage of social media when they have insufficient funds. Even though social media marketing strategy stays the same, the evolution of marketing styles has changed according to the consumer preferences, tastes and fashion. Each of the social platforms like Instagram, twitter, YouTube, snapchat, etc play a significant role without the limitations of legal boundaries.
- How does social media influence consumer behaviour, April 2021. Social media now is not about only

conversations, it is commerce. Social factors have played a vital role in consumer buying habits. By the ubiquity of smart phones and social network have taken word-of-mouth to new heights. Stats that prove social media influenced the consumer buying behaviour.

- ✓Forbes: 81% of consumers are influenced by their friends' social media posts.
 - ✓Stakla: 66% consumers have been influenced to buy from a new brand after seeing social media posts of other consumers.
 - ✓Forbes: 78% of consumers say companies' social media posts impact their purchases.
- Impact of Social Media Marketing Activities on Consumer Buying Behaviour for Casual Dining Restaurants in Sri Lanka, 2019 **Author:** Imali Fernando

The research paper mentions mainly about social media marketing it's strategies. Social media platforms like YouTube, Instagram, twitter, Facebook turn the company's strategy of marketing using latest marketing techniques. As the social media is open for all without any boundaries it is easy to promote their product. This study specifically mentioned the most influential dimensions like E word of mouth, interaction, visuals.

- A study of impact of social media on consumer behaviour in restaurant industry of Jaipur city, 2016 **Author:** Mredu Goyal Online visibility through social media is increasing gradually, it is becoming a secret source for restaurant owners in having strong customer base. As the consumer buying behaviour is changing frequently, marketers must change their strategies according to the changing needs of the consumers.
- The Instagram Effect: How social media impacts foodservice, 2021 **Author:** Sylvia Tomczak

This article mainly focused on how the Instagram is impacting the consumer preferences and their tastes in food.

Image 1: An image of Instagram explore page with reels

C. Consumer Preferences- Never Considered Constant

Consumer preference means an individual tastes of individual consumers. It changes according to the changing trend of the economy and many more factors. Consumer preference of a customer is never considered as constant in any of the markets. As the effect doesn't merely mean only positive or negative but comprises the possibility of both,

They have clearly mentioned about the rule of Instagram in the world over all other social media platforms. As the effect doesn't merely mean only positive or negative but comprises the possibility of both, the article further mentioned how Instagram can play a role in drawbacks in few of the cases. Thus, the article provides us with the changing preferences of the consumers especially in the food and beverages world through Instagram.

V. METHODOLOGY

This paper is completely unbiased. Keeping with the view of all the customer opinions using close ended questions, the primary data has been collected by circulating structured questionnaire. For the further analysis, the secondary data has been used. This research paper is with a pure objective to know more about how social media is ruling and changing the preferences and demands of the customers.

A. Research Gap:

- Focus on the research on the cafeterias in the area- Sainikpuri.
- Influence of food bloggers on consumer preferences compared to the Instagram pages of cafeterias.
- The new update of Instagram- THE REELS; easy and shortest way of food blogging.
- Word of mouth vs Instagram blogs.

B. Scope of the study

The research study is in and around of Sainikpuri of the Telangana state. Sainikpuri has been growing for 5 years in Secunderabad with the theme concept of cafe.

The statistics of Instagram after introducing reels is shown in the below diagram (source taken from influencer marketing hub)

the article further mentioned how Instagram can play a role in drawbacks in few of the cases. There is a numerous factor that can be discussed that change the preferences of an individual consumer, but as the research paper is limited to the extent of consumer preferences on cafeterias in Sainikpuri area, we don't do the deep study about consumer preferences as whole.

Talking about the consumer preferences about cafeterias first, we all know that cafeterias have different alternatives resting in the same area. But, why only few cafes are being popular even though there are number of cafeterias in the same locality? Why is that many of the times people often seek to try new ones? Every answer about the flickering preferences of a consumer can be understood by studying it.

D. Relation between Instagram and cafeteria

When it comes to cafe marketing Instagram is the visual platform right now as there is increase in its users. Whether you are starting a cafeteria or are into cafe business for a while Instagram helps you in this business for marketing. On Instagram you can promote your wares, communicate with customers, and attract new business.

While diners have eaten with their eyes first the popularity of social media especially Instagram has made flawless food presentations. The benefit of Instagram clicks

for cafeteria business had impacted both food presentation and restaurant design. Some cafes even create food with photography in mind for Instagram. On the other hand, there is a disadvantage also as cafes focus on photo friendly food rather ok flavour, customers lose out in the long run.

As Instagram is the visual platform for and the quality of your images and videos is the reflection towards the business. For cafes consistency is a big deal not only your quality of the video or image matters your Instagram page is also a reflection of this.

E. Increase in Users of Instagram from 2013-2021

As we can see from the below data, users of Instagram have gradually increased over past decade after its introduction into the social media world.

In 2013 the Instagram account holders were 110 million, last year it has increased to 1890 million users around the world.

Date	Users(mm)
2013	110
2014	200
2015	370
2016	500
2017	700
2018	1000
2019	1210
2020	1520
2021	1890

Table 1: Showing the increase in the users of Instagram.

Graph 1: Increase in the Instagram users

VI. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS:

Fig. 1: Percentage of male and female in the survey

From the above pie chart, we can see that 55.2 % are female and 44.8% are male.

Fig. 2: Showing the age group of different people

As we can see in the pie chart above age between 18-25 are in maximum number than other ages.

Fig. 3: Percentage of students and employees participated in the survey

From the above pie chart, we can see that 76.1% are students and 11.9% are employees.

Fig. 4: Percentage of users of Instagram

We can see that 95.5% of consumers use Instagram whereas only 4.5 % doesn't use Instagram.

Fig. 5: Percentage of people who visited cafeteria

From the above pie chart, we can see that 88.1% of consumers visited cafeterias.

VII. DATA ANALYSIS

Questions	Mean	Standard deviation
How often you do you visit cafeterias?	2.375	0.99
Do you watch food blogs of Sainikpuri cafeterias?	1.42	0.49
What do you believe the most to visit a cafeteria?	1.29	0.45
What type of food do you prefer the most in cafeterias?	3.04	1.48
What do you prefer the most in cafeterias	4.4	1.15
How many hours do you spend in a cafeteria?	2.16	1.11
What do you prefer to watch	1.96	0.17
Which one have you visited the following cafes in Sainikpuri?	4.36	3.16
Did you find any blogs related to the cafeterias in Sainikpuri	1.42	0.49
Do you follow the Instagram pages of the above-mentioned cafeterias?	1.802	0.39
Have you visited the following cafes because of Instagram?	21.83	4.37
How often do you face a challenge in finding a parking space at cafeterias	3.31	1.42
Would you be interested in reserving a parking spot in advance at cafeterias?	2.07	0.88
Is it true an Instagram is an incredible platform to promote cafeteria business?	1.73	1.15
Do you think cafeterias can build brand awareness by telling their followers of that page to their friends?	1.65	0.92

Table 2: Data analysis of various questions asked to the consumers through questionnaire.

A. Several Factors Affecting Business on Instagram with Consumer Preferences.

➤ Correlation Analysis:

- How many hours do you spend in a cafeteria? (X value)
- Is it true that Instagram is an incredible platform to promote cafeteria business? (Y value)

✓ **Correlation:** The value of R = 0.0424

Although technically a positive correlation, the relationship between variables is weak. (Nb the nearer the value is to zero, the weaker the relationship). Therefore, the existence of positive relationship shows that the Instagram affected the hours spent in cafeteria.

- Age (X value):
- What do you prefer the most in cafeterias? (Y value)

✓ **Correlation:** The value of R = -0.0573

Although technically a negative relationship, the relationship between the variables is only weak. (Nb, the nearer the value is to zero, the weaker the relationship). Therefore, the existence of negative relationship shows that the age affected the preferences in cafeterias.

➤ Food Blogging Through Reels:

Before the Instagram reels were introduced, the food blogs were created as a long video with a lot of explanation and were posted in different platforms like Instagram IGTV video, YouTube video or anywhere else.

This was quite time taking and people lost interest and patience to watch such a long video on food items. That is when Tik-Tok started getting popular and then the lockdown overall world. Banning of Tik-Tok made people more inattentive to watch the whole video of food blogs. That is

when the reels were introduced this changed the whole situation and perspective of many of the consumer preferences.

Food blogging is one such way to communicate with many people regarding one's own opinion and experience with food and surroundings in any cafes, restaurants Dhaba's etc. most of the cafeterias rely on the food blogger videos that go viral in social media. But since the reels have taken its place in the world, food blogging was easier to make.

A 30 second short video containing all information along with the location tagged with a positive response is all people need nowadays. According to the questionnaire we circulated among the people, 70.8% of the people voted for word of mouth from peers in the question "what do believe the most to visit a cafeteria?". Only 29.2 % opted social media. The responses we got from different age groups carrying social media accounts with them still don't believe everything completely.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion of this paper, we would like to appreciate the work and the newest ideas of cafeterias in Sainikpuri. They provide a huge fun and entertainment at any gathering sessions. The cafeterias in here treat us as a part of their family and never fails to be a home for everyone. While coming to the point of social media, we all know how vast the topic is. Social media surely is a game changer of the world, however, even after introducing all these latest updates in social media, people still believe the most in word of mouth from the people they trust. According to the questionnaire we circulated among the people, 70.8% of the people voted for word of mouth from peers in the question "what do believe the most to visit a

cafeteria?”. Only 29.2 % opted social media. The responses we got from different age groups carrying social media accounts with them still don't believe everything completely.

IX. FINDINGS

- Thus, at the end of the research paper, the researchers get to know about the various consumer preferences on the cafeterias found in Sainikpuri.
- This research paper has led the authors to know a lot about how social media is playing a gigantic role in the world of minds.
- The introduction of reels in Instagram lays a path to the latest version of food bloggings.

X. SUGGESTIONS

- Cafeterias took many forms over the decade. But the trends and expectations in the world keep on changing. Thus, the authors would like to suggest cafes to have updated information about latest trends and come up with a new version.
- According to the questionnaire we circulated, people often find it difficult to find a parking area near cafeterias in sainikpuri. Over 33.7% of the people often face the challenge of finding parking spaces near cafes. Thus, after the research, researchers would like to suggest the cafeterias to supply parking facilities, so that such a small thing won't affect the impression on café.
- Many cafeteria pages in Instagram [sainikpuri area] has less followers than the amount of people visiting them. Social media marketing is a key to the door of whole new world. Rather than depending on the food bloggers completely, a frequent communication with customers and followers through posting content on Instagram would help cafes get more popular.
- Over 65.6% of the people who filled questionnaire feel that by tagging insta page of the cafeteria would build a famous brand awareness among the large population and thus, maintaining an Instagram page with respectable number of followers is necessary.
- A cafeteria owner, employees must communicate with the customers even when they are not at the place. Having people from cafe, who can clear their doubts regarding cafeteria will build a strong bond between the café and customers.

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REFERENCES

- [1.] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/359931575_The_Impact_of_Instagram_Influencer_Marketing_in_the_Restaurant_Industry
- [2.] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342638389_Impact_Of_Social_Media_On_Consumer_Behaviour?enrichId=rgreq-4d3c5af9de8e3fe5ed75d800b7f30f87-XXX&enrichSource=Y292ZXJQYWdlOzM0MjYzODM4OTtBUzo5MDg4NTY5NTE1OTUwMDIAMSU5MzY5OTc5MTE0MA%3D%3D&el=1_x_2&esc=publicationCoverPdf
- [3.] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346081266_Impact_of_Social_Media_Marketing_Activities_on_Consumer_Buying_Behavior_for_Casual_Dining_Restaurants_in_Sri_Lanka
- [4.] https://core.ac.uk/display/84797241?utm_source=pdf&utm_medium=banner&utm_campaign=pdf-decoration-v1
- [5.] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358252939_The_Effects_of_Instagram_Marketing_Activities_on_Customer-Based_Brand_Equity_in_the_Coffee_Industry
- [6.] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339310919_Evaluation_of_Impact_of_Instagram_on_Customer_Preferences_The_Significance_of_Online_Marketing
- [7.] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346081266_Impact_of_Social_Media_Marketing_Activities_on_Consumer_Buying_Behavior_for_Casual_Dining_Restaurants_in_Sri_Lanka
- [8.] <https://www.nosto.com/blog/how-does-social-media-influence-customer-behavior/>
- [9.] <http://thecoffeecup.co.in/about-us>
- [10.] <https://globeweblist.com/a-brief-history-of-cafeterias-and-cafeteria-management/>
- [11.] <https://www.searchenginewatch.com/2020/11/20/how-social-media-influence-71-consumer-buying-decisions/>
- [12.] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349061145_ROLE_OF_SOCIAL_MEDIA_ON_CONSUMER_PREFERENCES
- [13.] <https://www.bing.com/search?q=https%3A%2F%2Fsocialmediaweek.org%2Fblog%2F2017%2F05%2Fsocial-media-%20influencing-purchase-decisions%2F&pc=0NAD&ptag=C24N2210A1D3A462C2B&form=CONBDF&conlogo=CT3210127>
- [14.] https://archive.org/details/perma_cc_CLQ7-LJ4A
- [15.] <https://medium.com/@maximilianharrison/how-social-media-is-influencing-purchase-decisions-a5467ae0a92d>